

DEONTOLOGY AS A KEY ELEMENT OF PROFESSIONAL ETHICS OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

Fomina Mayde Anatolevna

Assistant teacher of the Department of Languages,
Samarkand State Medical University
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Abstract. This article provides popular expressions, sayings, proverbs and sayings related to medical science, the concept of medical duty, and readiness to save people. A doctor must work on himself, improve his knowledge, and keep up with the times. The possibility of making mistakes should be reduced to zero. Every action of a doctor should be aimed at the benefit of the patient.

Key words: phraseological expressions, doctor's professional level, correct diagnosis, philanthropy.

Introduction

The main task of studying Latin in medical universities is to prepare a doctor who is capable of competently using Latin medical terminology in his practical and scientific activities. In addition to medical terms, the professional language of physicians contains special expressions used only in Latin: *in vivo* - on a living organism, *per os* - through the mouth, *pro narcosi* - for anesthesia, *per se* - in its pure form and other more complex phraseological expressions that future doctors must master. Modern methodological recommendations make it possible to become familiar not only with the necessary terminology, but also with proverbial phraseological expressions, which are of great importance both from the point of view of deontological and closely related ideological and political education.

Deontology, in turn, has a number of interdisciplinary connections, most of which have a parallel terminological apparatus with the fields of psychology, psycholinguistics, cultural studies and pragmatics. Phraseology is a branch of the science of language that studies the system of stable verbal complexes in its current state and historical development.

Results and discussion

This article provides stable figurative compound terms, catchphrases, aphoristic sayings, proverbs and sayings related to medical science and moral education. Each discipline, having its own specific characteristics, uniquely refracts the laws of deontology - the science of a doctor's duty, his duties and high morality.

The concept of medical duty can be understood very broadly - from honest, modest performance of everyday medical work to the manifestation of high courage in emergency circumstances, and even higher, to the willingness to sacrifice oneself to save people. It is not without reason that the famous Dutch physician Van Tulp proposed to make a burning candle a coat of arms, a symbol of a doctor - *Aliis inserviando consumor* - "while shining (serving) others, I burn myself." Latin teachers in their classes can use Latin sayings of ancient scientists on a medical topic, and use examples of their interpretation to introduce future doctors to medical ethics.

The features of medicine and the main representative of this science - the doctor - stem from their purpose, noble tasks - helping a sick person. The saying - *Noli nocere* - "Do no harm" (or *Primum non nocere* - "first of all, do no harm") sounds like the doctor's motto and a warning that every action of the doctor should be aimed at the benefit of the patient. Whatever research the doctor conducts, the basic principle of "*Noli nocere*" remains unshakable, which he must follow in his medical, practical and scientific activities. Here we can also cite the following phraseological saying: *Ne noceas si iuvare non potes* - "Do no harm if you cannot help."

The Latin phraseological combination - *chirurgus mente prius et oculis agat, quam manu armata* let the surgeon first act with his mind and eyes, and then with his armed hand - echoes the words of the outstanding Soviet surgeon S.S. Yudin that surgical work consists of two elements - the arts of handicraft and scientific thinking, which one without the other are fruitless. A bad surgeon is one whose hands work faster than his head. Patients are attracted to the doctor by his patient and sympathetic ability to question and listen to them: - *Qui bene interrogat, bene dignoscit* - whoever questions well makes a good diagnosis. Hence *Auscultare disce* - learn to listen carefully (listen), *Ausculata et perpende* - listen and weigh. A cordial conversation conducive to complete frankness, the opportunity to speak out, to express one's feelings, in themselves, cause some improvement in the patient's condition. *Dixi et animan levavi* - said and lightened the soul - says an old, but surprisingly correct and apt Latin proverb.

The authority of a doctor is ensured primarily by his professional level, therefore one of the most important responsibilities of a doctor is to work on himself, to improve his knowledge: *Per scientiam ad salutem aegroti* through knowledge to the health of the patient. *Ignorantia non est argumentum* - ignorance is not an argument (justification).

Ancient Chinese sages said that knowledge that is not improved decreases every day: - *Non progredi est regredi* - not going forward means going backward, says the Latin saying. And the Polish scientist T. Kelanowski said in 1968 that a doctor who does not look into a book should be feared more than the disease. *Libri amici, libri magistri* - books - friends, books - teachers; *Alit lectio ingenium* - reading nourishes the mind. If for many professions one can to some extent assume the legitimacy of the long-known Latin proverbial phraseology *Errare humanum est*, which means "it is human nature to err," then for a doctor the possibility of making a mistake should be reduced to zero, since an error in diagnosis and treatment can lead to irreparable consequences. If a doctor diagnoses correctly, treats skillfully, people go to him willingly, they are treated with confidence, for *Qui bene dignoscit bene curat* - whoever diagnoses well, treats well.

Diagnosis bona - curatio bona - good diagnosis - good treatment. Treatment of a patient will be successful if he trusts the doctor's qualifications, is confident in his desire to help, feels a sensitive attitude towards himself, if for the doctor - *Salus aegroti - suprema lex* - the health (good) of the patient is the highest law, if the doctor inspires the patient with hope for good - *Comple aegrotum bona spe* - inspire the patient with hope for good things. *Medicus amicus et servus aegrotorum est* - doctor - friend and assistant (servant) of the sick. In addition to abilities, knowledge and great hard work, a doctor must have a love of humanity. *Arte et humanitate, labore et scientia* - art and humanity, labor and knowledge should be the motto of doctors.

The famous French surgeon Rene Loriche wrote in 1966 that one must serve humanity, thinking only about its pain, suffering, vulnerability in the fight against illness, *Divinum opus - sedare dolorem*, the divine work of soothing pain. *Officium medici est, ut tuto, ut celeriter, ut iucunde sanet* - the doctor's duty is to treat safely, quickly, pleasantly (or in short *cito, tuto et iucunde* (Celsus) - quickly, safely and pleasantly).

Conclusion

When treating a patient, the doctor treats him not only as an organism, but also as a person. *Medice, cura aegrotum, sed non morbum* - doctor, treat the patient, not the disease, says the Latin phraseological saying. However, ancient doctors and historians, such as Plato and Galen, wrote about the extraordinary greed and selfishness of many famous doctors of their time.

Then the old Latin saying *Praemia cum poscit medicus satan est* appeared - the doctor Satan, when he demands a reward. Unfortunately, selfish doctors can still be found today. They are written about and exposed, which is why the ancient Latin saying of a phraseological nature - *Praemia cum poscit medicus satan ast* - has not lost its force today. Pride in the most noble, humane profession needed by people is fostered by such names as: *Omnium profecto artium medicina nobilissima* - of all the sciences (arts), medicine is certainly the noblest (Hippocrates) and *Medicina fructuosior ars nulla* - there is no science more useful than medicine (Pliny).

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